
Awareness of Breastfeeding Program among Mothers: Basis for Integrated Breastfeeding

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ABSTRACT

The Philippines is committed in achieving the Millennium Development Goals specifically to eradicate extreme poverty and hunger and also to reduce child mortality. This research was carried out to assess the awareness of the breastfeeding program among mothers in James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital. This study will be a basis for integrated breastfeeding management program of the hospital. A descriptive survey research of 98 mothers admitted at James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital, who were given health teaching about breastfeeding by the hospital's healthcare providers, was carried out. The questionnaires also include the profile of the respondents and their feedback on the breastfeeding program. This study showed that the mothers were aware of the importance of breastfeeding and the basics of breastfeeding but were slightly aware of the common breastfeeding problems. It revealed that the health care providers did not explain the importance of breastfeeding, there's a limited discussion on the basics of breastfeeding and the health care provider did not discuss the common breastfeeding problems. Healthcare providers have a duty to raise the awareness of mothers about breastfeeding through breastfeeding program. Mothers should be more educated and highly aware about the importance of breastfeeding, basics of breastfeeding and common breastfeeding problems for the mothers to fully achieve successful breastfeeding and to safeguard the health of both the mother and the baby. It can all be attained through the integrated breastfeeding management program of the hospital.

Keywords: Awareness, Breastfeeding, Mothers, Integrated breastfeeding management program

How to Cite (APA): Tinio, M.E., Gadia, E.D., & Quimen, V.C. (2023). Understanding the factors influencing prenatal care utilization and maternal health services satisfaction: Insights from pregnant women's attitude and experiences. *Journal of Scholarly Graduate Researches*, 1(1), 59-72. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14934223>

INTRODUCTION

Breastfeeding is recognized worldwide as being beneficial to both the mother and the baby. Breastfeeding is an action that is necessary. It's a talk about topic most especially when maternal and child is the concern. Ideally all mothers can breastfeed, provided they have an accurate information and support from their family and the health care system equipped with the right knowledge and skills in lactation management. Healthcare providers are the ones who have the responsibility in giving adequate information. But still, it is the mothers' choice and willingness to follow and accept the teachings and information given to them in the breastfeeding program.

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The Official Journal of the Institute of the Graduate Studies

Volume 1, Issue 1

January to December, 2023 Edition

As stated by James Grant (2023), Former Executive Director of UNICEF, breastfeeding is a natural "safety net" against the worst effects of poverty...it is almost as if breastfeeding takes the infant out of poverty for those first few months in order to give the child a fairer start in life and compensate for the injustice of the world into which it was born. According to the WHO Global Health Observatory data, 5.9 million children under age five died in 2015, around 16,000 every day. More than half of these early child deaths are due to conditions that could be prevented or treated with access to simple, affordable interventions. The leading causes of death in under-five children are pneumonia, preterm birth complications, intrapartum-related complications, diarrhea, birth asphyxia, malaria and congenital abnormalities. About one third of all child deaths are linked to malnutrition. Neonatal deaths accounted for 45% of under-five deaths in 2015. Breastfeeding has many positive benefits for mothers and their babies and is the ideal method of feeding and nurturing infants. Breastfeeding is not only free but also good for babies in their health to combat malnutrition. Human breastmilk is the most complete form of nutrition for infants and protects them from a wide array of infections and other health problems.

Breastfeeding is the national health strategy to protect infant health and save lives (DOH IYCF, 2011-2016). In the Philippines, 1 of 4 children under-five years of age are at risk of infection & death. The Department of Health (DOH) today urges all mothers to practice exclusive breastfeeding up to six months to reduce child mortality and improve child survival. Exclusive breastfeeding means that for the first six months from birth, nothing except breast milk will be given to babies (DOH, 2011). The timing of initiation of breastfeeding is important as there is a higher risk of death among infants with longer delay in the initiation of breastfeeding (Mullany et al., 2008). Whereas complementary feeding is the process starting when breast milk alone is no longer sufficient to meet the nutritional requirements of infants, and therefore other foods and liquids are needed, along with breast milk (WHO, 2016). Another article stressed that infant and young child feeding practices which include breastfeeding initiation, exclusive breastfeeding for six months and complementary feeding with continued and sustained breastfeeding are known to reduce under-five mortality rates by 20-25% (WHO, 2009). Exclusive breastfeeding is recommended up to six months of age, with continued breastfeeding along with appropriate complementary foods up to two years of age or beyond. A previous study by Asio (2019) also claimed that teenagers are aware of breastfeeding and its promotion.

In order for the mothers to be highly aware of breastfeeding to ultimately achieve successful breastfeeding, an institution needs a good breastfeeding program. The breastfeeding program promotes and supports public health and health care efforts to make breastfeeding the normal method of infant feeding in order to provide proven benefits to the mother, infant, and society.

Health teaching is one of the primary responsibilities of a nurse not only to prevent illness but also to promote wellness. It was known that breastfeeding is a learned skill that's why this action is learned by means of health education and enhanced by practice and support. Health teaching is included in the breastfeeding program and can elicit one's awareness. Through the mother's acquisition of knowledge and awareness from the breastfeeding program, it will enable them to practice breastfeeding successfully. Mothers were chosen as respondents since they are known for having this curiosity on certain actions that are related to their current situation.

To heighten the mothers' awareness about breastfeeding, the DOH together with its accredited hospitals and private sectors have concerted efforts in enhancing and strengthening breastfeeding programs to protect, promote and support breastfeeding.

In Olongapo City, James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital is a DOH accredited and a mother-baby Friendly Hospital. In line with the mandates of the DOH, James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital is a hospital that

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protects, promotes and supports rooming-in, breastfeeding and mother-baby friendly practices. The hospital's estimated number of newborn deliveries in the Delivery Room per day is 12 deliveries.

Despite national efforts to promote exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months after delivery, the majority of women provide water, glucose water and formula milk to their infants by the end of first month (NBS & ICF Macro, 2011). This may be due to cultural beliefs that breastmilk is not enough for infants. This is also caused by factors such as lack of self-security, breast soreness, poor infant positioning, mother's perception of inadequate milk supply and lack of necessary support and information from healthcare providers (WHO, 2001). It is likely that despite the laws and policies to promote breastfeeding, many mothers do not get effective information, advice and support regarding exclusive breastfeeding and continuation of breastfeeding.

This study was developed because of the interest of the researcher on the awareness of the breastfeeding program among mothers in James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital as a basis for integrated breastfeeding management program.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design that was used for this study is the descriptive design. Descriptive study describes a given state of affairs as fully and carefully as possible (Asio, 2021). It is used to describe systematically the facts and characteristics of a given population or area of interest, factually and accurately. This requires a more detailed analysis of the various aspects of phenomena and their interrelationships (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009). For example, the study of Asio and Jimenez (2021) and It is concerned with the conditions or relationships that exist, opinions that are held, processes that are going on, effects that are evident, or trends that are developing. The descriptive methodology used in this study is the survey research. Survey research obtains data to determine and summarize the specific characteristics of individuals or groups or physical environments (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009). Here, the researcher used a survey questionnaire for measuring the instrument in collecting data and to assess the awareness of the breastfeeding program among mothers in James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital. A descriptive survey involves asking the same set of questions (often prepared in the form of a written questionnaire or ability test) of a large number of individuals either by mail, by telephone, or in person (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2009). Thus, the main purpose and reason of the study was to assess the awareness of the breastfeeding program among mothers in James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital as a basis for integrated breastfeeding management program of the hospital.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the mothers at James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital, Olongapo City during Fiscal Year 2017. The researcher used non-probability sampling because it was very acceptable for this study. Non-probability sampling is a sampling technique where the samples are gathered in a process that does not give all the individuals in the population equal chances of being selected. There is also a risk that it may produce less accurate and misleading result. But base on the capability, experience, budget of the researcher and the time span that the research will take place, it is more convenient and practical like most of the sample in nursing research (Polit & Beck, 2006).

Particularly, the non-probability sampling used in the study is the purposive sampling. In purposive sampling, the researcher selects participants based on personal judgment about who will be most

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representative or informative (Polit & Beck, 2006). The researcher might decide purposely to select subjects who are judged to be typical of the population or particularly knowledgeable about the issues under study. In this study, the researcher's experience and knowledge about the population were used to hand pick and purposely select the participants which were the mothers. The researcher believes that the mothers were more suitable for the research compared to other individuals. The researcher ensures that the participants she questioned possess the desired information and that they were all willing to answer the questions. The number of respondents involved in this study was 98 mothers. The sample of the study was based on the number mothers currently admitted at James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital, Olongapo City.

Instrumentation

The main instrument in data gathering is a survey questionnaire consisting of three parts. The survey questionnaire regarding breastfeeding was understandable and in line with the capability of the mothers who participated in the study. The type of survey questionnaire used in the study measured the awareness of mothers with regards to the breastfeeding program. This helped to determine the additional information that the participants need.

The researcher requested the respondents, which were the mothers, to sign the informed consent prior to including them in the study. Then, once the consent was secured, the researcher utilized a survey questionnaire using a paper-pen questionnaire which was analyzed. Part 1 deals with the profile of the respondent which described their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, type of family, employment status, monthly family income, number of pregnancies, number of births, and number of times they have given birth in the hospital. Part 2 deals with the awareness of the breastfeeding programs among mothers. These categories were adapted from the DOH and others sources which includes the importance of breastfeeding, basics of breastfeeding and common breastfeeding problems. Part 3 deals with the content of the health teaching about breastfeeding given to the mothers by the healthcare providers in the hospital. Moreover, a pilot study was administered in OB Rooming-In Ward of James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital to determine the reliability and validity of each data indicate therein, before it was finalized.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data gathered were organized, tabulated and processed through the Microsoft Excel and Statistical Package for Social Sciences Version 20 (SPSS v.20). The following were the statistical treatment employed to answer the specific questions raised in the study: frequency distribution and percentage, weighted mean, descriptive rating, independent t-test and analysis of variance. Frequency distribution and percentage was used to organize and describe the personal profile of the respondents that includes the following: age, civil status, highest educational attainment, type of family, employment status and monthly family, number of pregnancies, number of live births, and number of times they have given birth in the hospital. Weighted mean and descriptive rating were used to describe the awareness of the breastfeeding program among mothers. Independent t-test was used to check if there is a significant difference between the respondents' type of family and awareness about breastfeeding. The required level of significance is 95%. Analysis of variance (F-Test) was used to check if there is a significant difference between the respondents' profile and awareness about breastfeeding. The required level of significance is 95%.

Ethical Consideration

The study strictly complies with the Data Privacy Act (Republic Act 10173), emphasizing the importance of protecting the privacy and confidentiality of all respondent information. The researcher is committed to

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the responsible handling of personal data, ensuring that it is securely stored and utilized exclusively for the study's intended purposes. No personal information will be disclosed or accessed without proper authorization, reflecting a deep respect for the dignity, privacy, and rights of all participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section showcases the results from the gathered data.

Profile of the Respondents

Age. Most of the respondents belong to 28 – 32 years old while the least belongs to 38 and above years old. In the Philippines, the mother's mean age at first birth is 23 years old however the median age at first birth among women is supposed to be under 25–29 years old (PSA, 2022). Furthermore, women getting pregnant in the Philippines are becoming younger and younger. This may contribute to the number of respondents in the below 17 years old bracket. Recent data from the Philippine Statistics Authority (2014) reveal that every hour, 24 babies are delivered by teenage mothers. One in ten young Filipino women age 15-19 has begun childbearing, around 8 percent of Filipino girls aged 15 to 19 are already mothers and another 2 percent are pregnant with their first child according to the results of the 2013 National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS).

Civil Status. Majority of the respondents are living common law while the least belongs to married group. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2013), there were 476,408 marriages registered in 2011 showing a decline of 1.3 percent from the previous year's figure of 482,480. Since 2009, the number of registered marriages in the country has been declining. This may explain to the number of respondents married being the least in the group and the respondents living common law being the highest in the group. Marital status also affects breastfeeding initiation and duration. Compared to unmarried women, married women have higher rates of breastfeeding. Married women are twice as likely to breastfeed as unmarried women (Chin et al., 2008; Thulier & Mercer, 2009). Young, single mothers are less likely to breastfeed exclusively on discharge from the hospital where they gave birth (BORN data 2015). In this study, majority of the respondents are living common law. A common law relationship is one in which two people live together but are not legally married to each other. For the relationship to be common law the couple must live together in a 'marriage-like' relationship, for example, by sharing finances, and publicly referring to themselves as partners or spouses. Support systems may be a great influence; if a woman views breastfeeding positively, and has support from her partner, she will be more likely to breastfeed (Persad & Mensinger, 2007). Though most of the respondents are living common law, still they have support from their partner in achieving successful breastfeeding.

Highest Educational Attainment. Most of the respondents are high school graduate while the least belongs to elementary level. Higher level of education among women may contribute to their high awareness about breastfeeding. On the other hand, one of the key determinants of the decline in breastfeeding in the Philippines is the increasing level of education among women, a factor which plays a role in the adoption of modern ideas, and which usually leads to the abandonment of traditional practices regarding child care (Caldwell, 2009).

Women of higher educational status also have higher rates of breastfeeding. In the study by Chin et al. (2008), women who graduated from high school were 70% more likely to breastfeed than those who did

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not; women who attended college were four times more likely to breastfeed than women who graduated from high school.

Type of Family. Majority of the respondents are extended family, seconded only by nuclear family. The role of supportive significant others in the breastfeeding mothers' life is very crucial. Family support is the mobilization and access to interpersonal resources that occurs when an individual attempts to deal with the stress and strains of life. The extended family is, in effect, the basic unit of Philippine society. Within given households, nuclear families average six to eight members in size. Unmarried adult daughters and sons typically remain in their parents' home and contribute to family support. Additional extended family members such as grandparents, aunts, uncles, or cousins also may live in the same house and assume vital roles.

Employment Status. Majority of the respondents are unemployed while the least belongs to self-employed. Maternal employment has been shown to decrease breastfeeding. Employment may also decrease breastfeeding because women in lower-status occupations may have more obstacles to expressing breast milk at work, or because women with hazardous occupations might be concerned their exposures might affect breast milk (Fein & Roe, 2008). Women involved in modern work, such as clerical, factory and professional jobs in the urban centers are often required to work away from home, thus reducing a mother's access to her child. On the other hand, women who are involved in traditional or informal work (agricultural activities, cottage industries and small-scale marketing (especially in the rural areas)), have more flexible schedules and this allows them to nurse their infants more often, thus maintaining longer periods of lactation (Huffman, 1984).

Monthly Family Income. Most of the respondents' income are P 6,000 and below while the least income belongs to P 12,001 – 15,000. The recommended average monthly income per year in Olongapo City is P142,923 or roughly P11,900 per month. The table suggests that majority of the respondents are below the recommended monthly income. This is in relation to the report conducted by Community Based Monitoring System (adopted by the local government units in 51 provinces, 502 municipalities and 39 cities covering at least 13,152 barangays in collaboration with the National Anti-Poverty Commission, the Department of Interior and Local Government and selected non-government organizations) saying that Olongapo City has 8,638 households or 19.6 % with income below poverty threshold compared to household with income below food threshold with 10.5% and household who experienced food shortage or 0.4%.

Most of the respondents' income are P 6,000 and below. Hence, they consistently continue breastfeeding even more and through it they can save money since they generally have lower income. Breastfeeding saves families time and money that would be spent on purchasing infant formula, bottles and fuel. For example, the average cost of feeding a six-month old baby for one month on infant formula is equal to at least the average household's monthly per capita income in many developing countries. Because breastfed babies are healthier than those who receive breastmilk substitutes, families save time and money that would be spent on visits to health practitioners and on purchasing medicines. In short, breastfeeding enables, families to achieve great self-sufficiency, thus reducing their dependency upon commercial products.

Number of Pregnancies. The respondents' number of pregnancies is 1 while the least belongs to 7, 8 and 9 births. The Family Planning Survey (2006) revealed that in 2006, 6 out of 10 married women, 15 to 49 years old, were at risk of conceiving a child with an elevated risk of mortality, both for the mother and the

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baby. These women were considered at risk either because they were impregnated at an early age (less than 18 years) or too old (age 35 or older) or have more than 3 previous births at an unacceptably short birth interval (less than 24 months). Some women need termination of their pregnancy due to maternal conditions. Some serious maternal conditions can cause abortion. The estimate was higher than the 2005 estimate of 50.6 percent (around 5 out of 10 women). It reveals that the number of pregnancies of women may not be equal to their number of births due to these factors.

Number of Births. This reveals that most of the respondents' number of births is 1 while the least belongs to 8 and 9 births. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2016), the number of births registered in 2014 had a total of 1,748,857, a decrease of about 0.7 percent compared to 1,761,602 births in 2013. In 2014, there was an average of 4,791 babies born daily or 200 babies born per hour or three babies per minute. The number of births from 2005 to 2014 showed an erratic trend. Mothers with high number of births are more aware and experienced about breastfeeding than mothers with lower number of births.

Births at JLGMMH. Majority of the respondents' births at JLGMMH is 1 while the least belongs to 9 births at the hospital. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2016), nine out of ten births were attended by medical professionals (Physician, Nurse, and Midwife) with 1,529,351 or 87.4 percent of total births. This marked an increase of 2.0 percent from last year's figure of 1,499,042 live births that were medically attended. Hilots/traditional birth attendants aided in the delivery of 205,571 or 11.8 percent of the total births. Most of the respondents' births at JLGMMH are only once. Giving birth in a hospital is by far the safest option for mothers. If the mother is high risk, it's the safest childbirth environment for her and her baby and if an unforeseen complication arises during labor such as a prolapsed cord or placenta abruption, for example.

Differences in the respondents' awareness about breastfeeding when grouped according to profile

Age. There is a significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to age. This means that there is enough sample evidence that mothers differ with one another in terms of their awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when they are grouped according to age.

Differences in the Respondents' Awareness about Breastfeeding when Grouped according to Civil Status

That there is a significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to civil status. One of the most important factors affecting the mothers' awareness and decision to breastfeed their babies is the partners' support (Wambach & Koehn, 2004).

Differences in the Respondents' Awareness about Breastfeeding when Grouped according to Highest Educational Attainment

That there is a significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to highest educational attainment. Maternal education may reflect more educated women being more likely to search out information on the health aspects of infant feeding choices; knowledge of the benefits of breastfeeding has been shown to predict breastfeeding (Chezem et. al., 2003). This may be related to increased access of information and recognition of the benefits of exclusive breastfeeding for mothers with higher education (Park et. al., 2003). Mothers who are knowledgeable and aware about the numerous health benefits of breastfeeding are more likely to breastfeed.

Differences in the Respondents' Awareness about Breastfeeding when Grouped according to Type of Family

There is no significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding between nuclear and extended family. This means that there is no sufficient sample evidence to prove that the nuclear family has higher awareness about the importance of breastfeeding than extended family.

Differences in the Respondents' Awareness about Breastfeeding when Grouped according to Employment Status

There is a significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to employment status. The amount of time a mother has to breastfeed is determined by her occupation. Employed women have lesser time to go to breastfeeding program that could decrease their awareness about the importance of breastfeeding whereas unemployed women have more time to go to breastfeeding program that could increase their awareness about the importance of breastfeeding.

Differences in the Respondents' Awareness about Breastfeeding when Grouped according to Monthly Family Income

There is a significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to monthly family income. Women with higher family income has also a higher-level education, hence they are more aware about the importance of breastfeeding.

Differences in the Respondents' Awareness about Breastfeeding when Grouped according to Number of Pregnancies

There is a significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to number of pregnancies. Higher number of pregnancies has been positively associated with higher awareness about the benefits of breastfeeding, breastfeeding initiation and more frequently with breastfeeding duration (Halowko, et al., 2018).

Differences in the Respondents' Awareness about Breastfeeding when Grouped according to Number of Births

There is a significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to number of births. Mothers with high parity have previous experience with breastfeeding that could make them more aware about the importance of breastfeeding. There are a greater number of women from the lower parity who terminate breastfeeding within two years as compared to women from higher parity. Primiparous women are less knowledgeable and skillful in breastfeeding; hence, they will usually seek assistance, advice, and help from health care professionals who generally promote breastfeeding. Furthermore, first time mothers are more likely to consider health promotion messages or be exposed to them in different ways.

Differences in the Respondents' Awareness about Breastfeeding when Grouped according to Births at JLGMH

There is no significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to births at JLGMH. This means that there is no enough sample evidence that mothers

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differ with one another in terms of their awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when they are grouped according to births at JLGMMH.

Feedback of mothers regarding on the breastfeeding program

Fifteen mothers wrote that the content of the health teaching that was given to them in the breastfeeding program are: Breastfeeding exclusively to the baby. Cleaning the nipples and breasts before breastfeeding. Breastfeeding the baby every 2-3 hours. The head of the baby should be elevated while breastfeeding. Burped the baby every after breastfeeding. It did not include the importance of breastfeeding and the common breastfeeding problems. One mother wrote, "The healthcare provider provided me health teaching about breastfeeding to increase my awareness about breastfeeding but the health care provider did not explain the importance of breastfeeding, there's a limited discussion on the basics of breastfeeding and the healthcare provider did not discuss the common breastfeeding problems."

Implications of the awareness of the breastfeeding program among Mothers in James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital

The results of this study will be a basis for integrated breastfeeding management program of the hospital. By assessing the awareness of the mothers, the healthcare providers will know the information that is lacking in the health teaching of the breastfeeding program that they are providing to the mothers. If there's information but limited, the healthcare providers can expound the topics and provide additional discussion or information about breastfeeding in the breastfeeding program to increase the awareness of the mothers. If totally there's no information given to the mothers in a certain topic, the healthcare providers should include it in the breastfeeding program. Through an Integrated Breastfeeding Management Program, health care providers could provide a holistic breastfeeding program that extends from the hospital to the mothers' home, community and employment. In doing so, it can strengthen the existing breastfeeding management program of the hospital ultimately for the mothers to achieve successful breastfeeding.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the findings the following conclusions are presented:

The profile of the respondents of the study showed that:

- The respondent's profiles in terms of age revealed that the highest number of mothers in the distribution are in the 28 – 32 age bracket.
- The respondent's profiles, in terms of civil status, revealed that the majority of the mothers lived under common law.
- The respondents' profiles regarding the highest educational attainment revealed that the highest number of mothers in distribution is from high school graduates.
- The respondents' profiles in terms of family type revealed that the majority of the mothers belonged to an extended family.
- The respondent's profiles in terms of employment status revealed that the majority of the mothers were unemployed.
- The respondent's profiles in terms of monthly family income revealed that most of the mothers' monthly family income was P 6,000 or below.

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- The respondents' profiles in terms of the number of pregnancies revealed that most of the mothers' number of pregnancies was one (1).
- The respondents' profiles regarding the number of births revealed that most mothers' birth numbers were one (1).
- The respondent's profiles regarding births at JLGMMH revealed that most of the mothers' births at JLGMMH were one (1).

The data gathered from the mothers surveyed in the awareness about breastfeeding the study showed that:

- The overall mean result of 2.83 implies that mothers were aware of the importance of breastfeeding.
- Regarding awareness about the basics of breastfeeding, the overall mean result of 3.16 implies that mothers were aware of the basics of breastfeeding.
- The overall mean result of 2.12 implies that mothers were slightly aware of common breastfeeding problems.

In the differences in the respondents' awareness about breastfeeding when grouped according to profile, the study showed that:

- There was a significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to age, civil status, highest educational attainment, employment status, monthly family income, number of pregnancies, and number of births. There was no significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the importance of breastfeeding when grouped according to type of family and births at JLGMMH.
- There was a significant difference in the mothers' awareness about breastfeeding basics when grouped according to highest educational attainment and monthly family income. There was no significant difference in the mothers' awareness about breastfeeding basics when grouped according to age, civil status, type of family, employment status, number of pregnancies, and number of births at JLGMMH.
- There was no significant difference in the mothers' awareness about the common breastfeeding problems when grouped according to age, civil status, highest educational attainment, type of family, employment status, monthly family income, number of pregnancies, number of births, and births at JLGMMH.

The data gathered from the mothers' feedback regarding the breastfeeding program revealed that the healthcare providers did not explain the importance of breastfeeding, there was a limited discussion of the basics of breastfeeding, and the healthcare providers did not discuss the common breastfeeding problems.

Based on the result of the findings, the following recommendations are presented:

1. Conduct a similar study in other settings to understand if there is a variation in the awareness of the breastfeeding program among mothers in the respondents of different hospitals.
2. Execute the study much longer and have more respondents in a specific place. More reliable research findings must be obtained to assess the mothers' full awareness of breastfeeding, and all biases must be controlled. The results would be beneficial in informing what needs to be addressed concerning how and when the breastfeeding program should be provided to mothers.
3. Do further exploration regarding the topic to enhance the study's validity and reliability. Also, more scrutinized research should be implemented in a clinical setting.
4. Healthcare providers need to identify at-risk women and intervene with appropriate interventions to promote breastfeeding. Healthcare providers may be uniquely positioned to assist women between hospital discharge and postpartum. Intervening early with a woman who is having difficulty breastfeeding may prevent breastfeeding discontinuation. Common reasons for

breastfeeding discontinuation can be anticipated, and interventions can be initiated quickly. Professional support from health care providers like doctors, nurses, and other practitioners can educate women about the importance of breastfeeding, the basics of breastfeeding, and common breastfeeding problems and provide the support they need to become confident and committed to breastfeeding continuation and to achieve successful breastfeeding.

5. During the breastfeeding program, healthcare providers should ask questions to mothers on topics that they are not aware of about breastfeeding. Healthcare providers should include the importance of breastfeeding, give additional discussion or information on the basics of breastfeeding, and include the common breastfeeding problems in the breastfeeding program. Healthcare providers should raise mothers' awareness of breastfeeding. In strengthening the breastfeeding program of the hospital, the awareness about breastfeeding among mothers will increase from being unaware, slightly aware, and aware to be highly aware.
6. Develop an integrated breastfeeding management program that will enable mothers to continue and achieve successful breastfeeding after hospital discharge, in the home and community, and during employment. The program will be extended from the hospital to the mothers' homes, communities, and employment.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study is limited to assess the awareness of the breastfeeding program among mothers in James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital during fiscal year 2017 as a basis for integrated breastfeeding management program. It is delimited to mothers as respondents of this study. This study has taken into consideration the age, civil status, highest educational attainment, type of family, employment status, monthly family income, number of pregnancies, number of births, and number of times they have given birth in the hospital. The respondents were chosen purposively, 98 mothers currently admitted at the OB Rooming-In Ward of James L. Gordon Memorial Hospital from April 10-18, 2017. The researcher used a survey questionnaire as the main instrument in gathering data and information to mothers. The implementation itself for attaining the desired number of respondents and the overall gathering and collation of data took effect for 2 weeks.

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The Official Journal of the Institute of the Graduate Studies

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